

EXPERIENCE OF CONDUCTING EDUCATIONAL CONSULTATIONS FOR FOREIGN STUDENTS OF I. HORBACHEVSKY TNMU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6937080>

Garlitska N.,

*Ph.D., Associate Professor, Department of General Chemistry,
I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, Ternopil, Ukraine*

Kachur O.

*Ph.D., Assistant Professor, Department of General Chemistry,
I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, Ternopil, Ukraine*

Abstract

The article covers the issue of organizing educational consultations for foreign students of I. Horbachevsky TNMU. The practice of using various types of consultations is disclosed. It has been established that the most effective consultations for assimilation and understanding of the educational material by a foreign student are consultation-explanation and consultation-discussion. The features of conducting educational counseling at the General Chemistry Department are described and recommendations are developed regarding the organization of educational consultations for foreign students.

Keywords: consultation, foreign students, educational process.

Introduction. Nowadays, the volume of information necessary for assimilation by the younger generation for normal life activities is growing significantly, which increases the role of educational consultations. Interest in consulting students has increased over the last decade; existing research suggests students have valuable perspectives on teaching and learning which teachers can usefully draw upon to inform thinking and planning. The analysis of scientific studies of the problem of organizational work of students at the theoretical and methodological level is highlighted in works of well-known teachers: A. Aleksyuk, S. Arkhangelsky, Yu. Babansky, V. Bezpalk, P. Pidkasysty, psychologists: A. Petrovsky, O. Leontiev and methodologists: O. Bilyaev, L. Palamar, M. Pentylyuk, K. Plysko. The works of S. Domnich, Ye. Tanko, N. Skrypnyk, L. Prokofyeva, T. Osypova, I. Barteneva, O. Bila, S. Shykhhalova, etc., are devoted to various forms of extracurricular work with students [1].

The internationalization of education is one of the most characteristic features of the development of education in the world during last decades. Creating favorable conditions for accelerating the internationalization of education in Ukraine and, first of all, for significantly increasing the number of foreign students in domestic higher educational institutions is one of the most important ways of international activity of Ukrainian educational institutions.

International students enrich higher education by bringing their languages, cultures, and perspectives to their peers and, in so doing, heighten social awareness, cultural literacies, and broad intellectual development for everyone [4, 6]. However, while international students contribute much to development of the educational process, they also confront many challenges. Adjusting to higher educational settings is a challenge for students from any cultural or academic background, but international students often face additional difficulties. The most serious factor for foreign students is the difficulty in preparing for classes, therefore the support and help of teachers in studying the educational material are very important.

The aim of this article consists in highlighting experience of conducting educational consultations for foreign students by teachers of the General Chemistry Department I. Horbachevsky TNMU.

Statement of the topic. In modern foreign psychological and pedagogical literature (J. F. Bugental, K. Bucnall, M. Hemm and D. Adams), the term "consulting" is correlated with the term "guidance", which is interpreted as "soft" or "easy" guidance, based on students requests [2]. The task of the consultant consists in providing assistance to the subject of teaching, to solve a problem situation on his initiative.

Consultation is a form of educational activity that involves providing students of the necessary assistance in assimilating theoretical knowledge and developing practical abilities and skills through the teacher's answers to specific questions or explanations of certain theoretical provisions or aspects of their practical application.

Today, there are many types of consultations that can be presented in the following classification [5]:

1. Counseling based on the subject orientation: individual, pair, small groups, groups.
2. Counseling by an appointment: organizational, methodical, informational, substantive.
3. Counseling according to the level of interactive interaction: mono-directional (consultations are received only from the teacher), interactive (consultations are also provided by students); integrated (the teacher must comment on consultations provided by the students).
4. Counseling based on a differentiated approach: for students who engaged in individual research work in the discipline; for students who confidently master the educational material on their own; for students who experiencing certain difficulties while performing independent work; for students who generally can not cope with the educational material on their own.
5. Counseling by time of holding: according to the approved schedule, non-systematic (if there is an initiative on the part of students or in case of need).

The importance of consultation and counseling is also proven by the fact that, according to regulatory documents, mandatory consultations at the full-time department make up 6% of the total number of hours allocated to the study of a specific academic subject [1].

In Ukraine, which ranks high among developed European countries in terms by the total number of students, medical and pharmaceutical specialties are the most popular among foreign citizens. Today 16 higher medical educational institutions of Ukraine carry out preparation foreign specialists [2], one of which is Ternopil National Medical University. The first international students got enrolled at the Ternopil State Medical Academy in September 1997. Since then, their numbers at our University have been increasing steadily: in the academic year 2020/2021, near 2500 international students from about 60 countries are studying at Ternopil National Medical University. About 80% of the teaching staffs of TNMU have certificates of English proficiency.

The most serious stress factors for foreign students are difficulties in preparing for classes, peculiarities of the pedagogical system of the educational institution, climatic differences, and remoteness of the family, less chance than in the student's homeland to be involved in social life of the educational institution, the city or the country. At the same time, mastering the profession of a doctor, performing one's professional activities requires a high level of professional and communicative competences from foreign students. Therefore, the teaching staff of the General Chemistry Department provides both academic and moral support to foreign students in the educational process.

The student and teacher relationship is important to build the students' academic life. It is important that a structure in the university design to promote student-teacher relationship. The teacher and students share how they are feeling. The teacher teaches on collaborative skills, facilitates group discussions and activities to confront issues of diversity in the context of the students' curriculum [3].

Based on the experience of providing consultations for foreign students, teachers may unconsciously speak quickly because they are familiar with their subject and they may extemporaneously pursue tangential subjects with cultural references that are unique to their home culture. Taking into account this factor, teachers of the General Chemistry Department uses slower speech, explain cultural features and periodically pause to take notes of the necessary material. Therefore, it contributes to better understanding and assimilation of difficult topics by foreign students.

The classroom experience is also challenging, since international students often confront a culture of teaching and learning in higher education that is substantially different from that to which they are accustomed [2, 4]. Due to cultural differences across educational systems, some international students may be accustomed to a teacher-centered classroom. When they enter classrooms that emphasize modes of self-directed or collaborative learning, such as student-led discussions, they may need additional help understanding the rationale and structure for participation.

The implementation of educational counseling at the General Chemistry Department takes place with using certain rules and requirements:

1. Maximum expression of interest in the topic that a foreign student seeks to solve.
2. Positive attitude to a foreign student during the counseling process.
3. The possibility of a foreign student choosing a strategy for solving a problem in the process of interaction.
4. Relying on the self-actualization tendency of a foreign student in solving a problematic task.

In the educational and methodological activities, teachers mainly use such consultations as: introductory, current and final. Introductory consultations are held before the beginning of practical classes. At them, the teacher gives advice on how to prepare for practical classes, introduces the requirements for the preparation of documentation (writing the protocol of a practical class), and provides recommendations for studying an educational material.

Current consultations are held from the first days of the academic year. Usually, each teacher appoints days and time of consultations. Every foreign student who has difficulties in learning the initial material can come at the appointed time (according to the schedule) and get help from the teacher in solving situational tasks. It is worth noting that a medical student has the right to independently choose the teacher from whom he wants to receive a consultation.

Final consultations are scheduled before tests or exams, only those students who have to take the final test the day before are present. Final consultations are often conducted in the question-and-answer form and in the interview form. In the first case, the teacher answers students' questions, and in the second case, the conversation is conducted on main questions proposed by both students and teachers.

The teachers of the General Chemistry Department determined that consultations, which held before the exam, it is advisable to organize twice, not once. At the first consultation, foreign students are told: how to prepare for the exam; procedure for its implementation; requirements for students' appearance at an oral interview; what you should pay attention to when preparing for the exam. This gives an opportunity to the foreign student better orientates and prepares for the examination methodology at TNMU. After the end of practical classes, no later than a day before the exam, a second consultation is held, at which the teacher answers the students' questions, puts forward individual situational tasks and organizes their discussion with the students.

Scientists divided consultations according to the method of conducting them: consultation-advice, consultation-clarification, consultation-discussion and mixed consultation [5]. Based on the experience of conducting educational consultations for foreign students, the most effective are consultation-clarification and consultation-discussion.

During the consultation-clarification process, foreign students ask questions related to clarifying the content of scientific and chemical provisions, new concepts. This type of the consultation is conducted in a

question-and-answer format and is assigned by the teacher after studying the section of the academic discipline in order to systematize students' knowledge or before a differentiated test or an exam.

Medical students come to the consultation after familiarizing themselves with the educational and methodological literature. First of all, the teacher answers such questions, which foreign students did not find answers to in preparation materials for the class. Having made sure that the foreign student has understood the basics and can continue studying the educational material on his own, the teacher limits himself to explain main provisions.

Consultation-discussion differs in its structure and purpose. As a result of conducting such an educational consultation, the teacher determines the degree of understanding and assimilation of the material by medical students. At the same time, the teacher points out shortcomings in foreign students' knowledge, notes what would be paid attention to in further work on the topic and recommends additional literature.

The value of consultation-discussion increases due to the growth of independent work of students. The number of consultations-discussions is determined depending on the volume of material allocated for independent study. Consultations are not conducted on all topics, but only on the most complex ones, important in the further educational and practical activities of future doctors.

Teachers of the General Chemistry Department conducted group and individual consultations with foreign students. By attending individual consultations, students learn the relationship between general and special disciplines when solving chemical situational problems. The teacher gives a non-standard task to the medical student. This contributes to the activation of mental activity, develops sustainable interest in the discipline being studied. Group consultations are held during preparation for exams or differentiated credits.

Taking into account the experience of conducting educational consultations for foreign students, teachers of the General Chemistry Department developed recommendations for conducting educational consultations and requirements for their organization:

1. Preparation of the teacher for each consultation (analysis of recommended literature for students; thinking through the forms, methods and structure of the consultation).

2. The consultation would not turn into a control of students' knowledge (strict administrative tone and mocking of shortcomings are unacceptable).

3. Consultations are held after classes, according to the schedule or by prior agreement with the teacher.

4. The student can choose a problem solving strategy during the counseling process.

5. The teacher relies on the student's self-actualization tendency in solving the problem task.

Conclusions. The most stressful factor for foreign students is difficulties in preparing for classes. Therefore, teachers of the General Chemistry Department provide support to medical students in the educational process; in particular, they conduct various types of consultations. In the educational and methodological activities, teachers use educational consultations: according to the didactic purpose (introductory, current and final), according to the method of conducting (consultation-clarification and consultation-discussion), according to the number of students (individual and group). The teachers have developed recommendations for conducting educational consultations and requirements for their organization.

References:

1. Fedorenko N. Peculiarities of the organization of individual and consultative work of a teacher of the higher education institution. *Bulletin of the National Academy of the State Border Service of Ukraine. Series: Pedagogy.* 2015. Vol. 4. P. 42–48 [in Ukrainian].

2. Kalashnik N. V. Peculiarities of educational work with foreign students in higher medical educational institutions of Ukraine. *Bulletin of Ivan Franko Zhytomyr State University.* 2016. Vol. 83, No 1. P. 60–66 [in Ukrainian].

3. Lenz B., Wells J., Kingston S. *Transforming schools: using project-based learning, performance assessment, and common core standards.* San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass, 2015. 312 p.

4. Luo J., Jamieson-Drake D. Examining the educational benefits of interacting with international students. *Journal of International Students.* 2013. Vol. 3, No 2. P. 85–101.

5. Tykhonovych V. The experience of conducting educational consultations for students of domestic higher educational institutions (70s – 90s of the 20th century). *Theory and methods of teaching and educational: a collection of scientific works / edited by a member-cor. National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine A. V. Trotsko.* Kharkiv: KhNASU, 2015. Vol. 37. P. 135–144.

6. Wong A. Should America's universities stop taking so many international students? *The Atlantic*, 2018. URL: <https://www.theatlantic.com/education/archive/2018/06/international-students/563942/> (accessed 19/07/2022).